

Influence of Work Environment and Discipline on the Performance of Non-Naked Health Employees of the Dr. Lung Hospital Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine and analyze the influence of the work environment and discipline, both simultaneously and partially, on the performance of non-health workers at Pulmonary Hospital Dr. Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor. This research design uses descriptive and verification research methods. The sampling technique uses non-probability sampling techniques. The number of respondent was 61 people. The subject of this research were non-health workers at Pulmonary Hospital Dr. Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor, and the object of this research is the work environment, discipline and employee performance. The tools used in this analysis are multiple regression analysis, multiple correlation analysis, coefficient of determination analysis, and hypothesis testing (F test and t test). The research results show that employee responses to work environment variables are in the good category, discipline is in the good category, and employee performance is in the good category. Partially or simultaneously, the work environment, discipline and employee performance have a significant and positive influence on the performance of non-health workers at Pulmonary Hospital Dr. Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor.

INTRODUCTION

Companies can achieve their desired goals with the intervention of human resources. With these factors, the company can achieve the success it wants to achieve. According to Hasibuan (2019:10), human resource management is the science and art of managing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they are effective and efficient and help realize the goals of the company, employees and the surrounding community. According to Bangun (2016:231), performance is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements (job needs). According to Ferawati (2017; 01), some factors influence performance including: Work environment, work discipline, work stress, renewal, and job satisfaction. According to Nitisemito (2013: 183), the work environment is everything that is around workers and that can influence them in carrying out the assigned tasks. The work environment is a valuable aspect in shaping employee performance which has a direct influence on employees in carrying out their work. In the formation of a quality environment, it shows the success of an organization and if the work environment is not good it will cause a lack of encouragement and even passion for work which will result in employee performance decreasing.

Apart from the work environment, another factor that influences employee performance is discipline. According to Sinambela (2018:336), discipline is a tool that leaders use to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change their behavior and to increase awareness and a person's willingness to obey all regulations and social norms that apply in a company. Discipline is believed to be a training process for employees in carrying out work so that employees can develop self-control and increase employee effectiveness at work so that discipline can be used as a benchmark in assessing the high and low levels of employee performance (Hasibuan, 2017: 193).

Dr. Lung Hospital M. Goenawan Partowidigdo (RSPG), is a public sector organization engaged in the field of health services which has the task of carrying out health efforts efficiently and effectively by prioritizing or prioritizing efforts to cure, restore and prevent disease as well as efforts to improve health. The types of health services provided include the emergency department (IGD), outpatient care consisting of 16 polyclinics, inpatient care and medical support.

Employees at Dr. Hospital M. Goenawan Partowidigdo (RSPG) consist of PNS (Civil Servants), CPNS (Civil Servant Candidates), BLU (Public Service Agency) and contract employees. Civil servants are employees who have fulfilled the specified requirements, are appointed by an authorized official are entrusted with duties in a state position are entrusted with other state duties, and are paid based on applicable laws and regulations. CPNS are employees who have just passed the first stage of the Civil Servant Candidate selection test. Candidates for Civil Servants have not yet fulfilled their obligations to fulfill the requirements as civil servants with a salary. They are paid a percentage based on the CPNS Decree which has been determined based on the laws in force in Indonesia. Non-PNS employees are BLU employees who have fulfilled the specified requirements, are appointed by authorized officials and

are paid based on applicable provisions to meet the personnel needs of the UPT PPK-BLU which are not met by civil servants. Contract employees are employees with non-permanent status or employees who only work for a certain time based on an agreement between the employee and the employing company.

The increasingly advanced development of hospitals means that hospital management can provide quality services to create patient satisfaction. The hospital tries to make optimal use of existing resources and minimize every form of patient complaint that comes by providing integrated services. Every effort was made by Dr. Hospital. M. Goenawan Partowidigdo (RSPG) to provide health services to fulfill the needs and desires of patients, as well as the accuracy of delivery in keeping with patient expectations. However, it turns out that the services provided to patients are not optimal, there are still patients who complain about health services. Paying attention to good employee performance will help the hospital become better known to many patients. Considering the importance of the work environment and discipline, it has an important influence on improving performance in hospitals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

According to Bintoro (2017: 15), "human resource management is a science or method of managing the relationships and roles of resources (workforce) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the common goals of the company and employees are achieved and society becomes optimal".

Work Discipline

According to Sinambela (2018:335), work discipline is the awareness and willingness of employees to comply with all organizational regulations and applicable social norms.

Work Discipline Indicators

The other indicators according to Sinambela (2018:356), are as follows:

- a. Frequency of Attendance
- b. Level of Awareness
- c. Ketaatan Pada Standar Kerja
- d. Compliance with Work Regulations
- e. Work Ethics

Work environment

According to Nitisemito (2013: 183), the work environment is everything that is around workers and that can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks.

Work Environment Indicators

According to Nitisemito (2013: 159), the work environment indicators are:

- a. Work Atmosphere
- b. Employment Relations
- c. Work Facilities

Performance

According to Bangun (2016:231), performance is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements.

Performance Indicators

According to Bangun (2016:231), various indicators or performance criteria that can be used to evaluate performance are:

1. Number of Jobs
2. Quality of Work
3. Timeliness
4. Collaboration Ability

Hypothesis Development

H1: Work environment and discipline have a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

H2: There is a positive and significant influence of the work environment on employee performance.

H3: There is a positive and significant influence of discipline on employee performance.

METHODOLOGI

Research design

The design of this research uses a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2016: 8) a quantitative approach can be interpreted as a research method based on positive philosophy, used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, and quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. The type of research is descriptive research and verification methods. According to Sugiyono (2016: 147), the descriptive method is a method used to describe the condition or value of one or more variables independently. Meanwhile, the verification method is a research method carried out on a certain population or sample to test a predetermined hypothesis.

Variable Operationalization

The operationalization of research variables explains the types of variables as well as a description of the variables studied in the form of variable titles, sub-variables, variable indicators, variable sizes and scales for measurement used in this research. According to Sugiyono (2017:38), a variable is anything in any form that is determined by the researcher to be studied so that information about it is obtained, then conclusions are drawn. According to Sugiyono (2017:39), independent variables are variables that are often referred to as stimulus, predictor and antecedent variables. According to Sugiyono (2017:39), the dependent variable is a variable that is influenced or becomes a consequence, because of the existence of the independent variable.

Table 1. Variable Operationalization

No	Variable	Variable Concept	Indicator	Item Statement	Measuring scale
1	Work environment (X ₁)	The work environment is everything that surrounds workers and that can influence them in carrying out their assigned tasks. (Nitisemito, (2013:183)	1. Work atmosphere 2. Employment Relations 3. Work Facilities (Nitisemito (2013:159)	1-2 3-4 5-6	Ordinal
2	Discipline (X ₂)	Discipline is a tool that leaders use to communicate with employees so that they are willing to change behavior and to increase awareness and a person's willingness to obey all the rules and social norms that apply in a company. (Sinambela, 2018:336)	1. Frequency of attendance 2. Level of employee alertness 3. Adherence to work standards 4. Compliance with work regulations 5. Work ethic (Sinambela, (2018:356)	7-8 9-10 11-12 13-14 15-16	Ordinal
3	Employee Performance (Y)	Employee performance is the result of work achieved by a person based on job requirements. (Wake, (2016:231)	1. Number of jobs 2. Quality of work 3. Punctuality 4. Presence 5. Collaboration ability (Bangun, (2016:231)	17-18 19-20 21-22 23-24 25-26	Ordinal

Samples and Sampling Techniques

According to Sugiyono (2016: 71), the sample size depends on the level of accuracy or error tolerance desired by the researcher. However, the error tolerance levels in general are 1%, 5% and 10%. The greater the error tolerance level, the smaller the number of samples and vice versa, the smaller the error tolerance level, the greater the number of samples obtained. The error tolerance level for obtaining samples in this research is 10%, so to determine the number of samples the Taro Yamane (1967) formula in Sugiyono (2016:158) is used as follows:

$$n = \frac{162}{162 \times (0,1)^2 + 1}$$

$$= 61,8 \text{ (61 Person)}$$

Based on the results of sample calculations using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula, the number of samples obtained was 61.8 samples and will be rounded up to 61 respondents.

Data analysis method

Data were analyzed using descriptive analysis, namely to determine the description of the characteristics of the respondents who would be asked about via questionnaire, thereby producing frequency values and average values (mean). The techniques used to analyze data are multiple regression, multiple correlation coefficient, coefficient of determination, F test and t-test.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity testing is carried out to measure statements or questions in the questionnaire. The validity of data is declared fulfilled if the statement or question can reveal something. The results of the validity test were carried out on 61 non-health workers at Dr. Lung Hospital. Goenawan Partowidigdo shows that all statements for each indicator are declared valid because they have a correlation value that is by the provisions, namely count is greater than or equal to table (count $\geq$ table) where the table value is 0.3. Based on instrument testing, it proves that purchasing decisions, price perceptions and distribution channels obtained reliable results because they have Cronbach's Alpha $\geq$ 0.6.

Classic assumption test

The classical assumption test aims to ensure that the research results are valid with the data used being theoretically unbiased. Consistent and efficient interpretation of regression coefficients. Based on the classical assumption test, the results obtained are: a) normality test, with the results of the data being declared to be normally distributed, b) multicollinearity test, in the regression model there are no symptoms of multicollinearity, c) heteroscedasticity test, the regression model is free from heteroscedasticity. So we can proceed to the multiple linear regression test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Employee Characteristics

Table 2 Recapitulation of Employee Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Employee	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Men	73,77%
2	Age	26-35 Old	39,34%
3	Employment status	Non health worker	100%
4	Last education	SMA	44,26%

Characteristics of the majority of employees are men aged 26-35 years with a high school education and work status as non-health workers. The following is a recapitulation of employee responses to the work environment and employee discipline and performance which can be seen in the table below:

Table 3 Recapitulation of Assessment of Work Environment Variables

No	Indicator	Average Score	Category	Interpretation
1	Work atmosphere	3,35	Pretty good	Employees feel that the working atmosphere at the company is quite supportive in supporting good work performance.
2	Work relationship	3,45	Good	employees receive attention from leaders in the form of work motivation and good relationships with fellow employees, making them comfortable at work
3	Work Facilities	3,38	Pretty good	Employees feel quite helped by the work facilities provided by the company to complete their work.
	Average Employee Response to the Work Environment (X1)	3,39	Pretty good	Employees feel the work environment at Dr. Lung Hospital. Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor overall is good enough to provide comfort and enthusiasm for work

Source: Data is processed, 2022

Based on Table 3 of the recapitulation, it can be seen that employee responses to the work environment show an average value of 3.39 in the quite good category. The work relationship indicator has the highest score, namely 3.45 in the good category, meaning employees have good relationships with employees, leaders and other employees. Meanwhile, the work facilities indicator has the lowest score of 3.35 in the quite good category, meaning that the work facilities provided by the company do not support the work, only the equipment available is sufficient for employees to use to help complete the work. The recapitulation of non-health workers' responses to the assessment of disciplinary variables for non-health workers is as follows:

Table 4. Recapitulation of Discipline Variable Assessment

No	Indicator	Average Score	Category	Interpretation
1	Frequency of Attendance	3,46	Good	Employees come to work according to the time determined by the company so that the number of late arrivals to work is quite small
2	Level of Alertness	4,29	Pretty Good	When working, employees are always careful in completing work and on the other hand are always careful in using company work equipment.
3	Adherence to Work Standards	3,45	Good	Employees understand and comply with work procedures and SOPs, accompanied by good ability and responsibility in completing work.
4	Compliance with Work Regulations	3,76	Baik	Employees have a good awareness of following and obeying all company regulations related to work

5	Work Ethics	4,44	Pretty Good	The majority of employees have good attitudes by complying with the norms that apply to the company and maintaining good relationships with fellow employees.
	Average Employee Response to Discipline (X2)	3,88	Good	Non-health workers at Dr. Lung Hospital Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor currently have good discipline.

Source: Data is processed, 2022

Based on Table 4 of the recapitulation, it can be seen that employee responses to discipline show an average value of 3.88 in the good category. The work ethics indicator has the highest score, namely 4.44 in the very good category, meaning employees comply with all norms that apply to the company and always maintain good relationships with fellow employees. Meanwhile, the frequency of attendance indicator has the lowest score of 3.45 in the good category, meaning that there are still some employees who come to work late due to certain factors. The recapitulation of non-health workers' responses to the assessment of employee performance variables is as follows:

Table 5. Recapitulation of Performance Variable Assessment

No	Indicator	Average Score	Category	Interpretation
1	Number of Jobs	4,09	Good	Employees can complete the work assigned by the company and meet the work targets that have been set.
2	Employee Quality	3,61	Good	Employees have quality work by meeting the work standards set by the company and achieving good results.
3	Punctuality	3,38	Pretty Good	Employees can complete work according to the time target determined by the company.
4	Collaboration Ability	4,39	Very good	The majority of employees have good collaboration skills in completing work
	Average Employee Response to Employee Performance (Y)	3,86	Good	Non-health workers at Dr. Lung Hospital Goenawan Partowidigdo Cisarua Bogor have performed very well.

Source: Data is processed, 2022

Based on Table 5 of the recapitulation, it can be seen that employee responses to performance show an average value of 3.86 in the good category. The collaboration ability indicator has the highest score, namely 4.39 in the very good category, meaning that employees have good collaboration skills in completing the work given by the company. Meanwhile, the indicator for the number of jobs has the lowest score of 3.38 in the quite good category, meaning that several employees have not been able to complete the work according to the targets set by the company.

Simultaneous Influence of Work Environment and Discipline on Employee Performance

Consumer responses regarding the location variable have the following recapitulation:

1. The access indicator has an average value of 4.09, including in the strategic category.
2. The visibility indicator has an average value of 3.79 including in the strategic category.
3. The traffic indicator has an average value of 3.75 including in the strategic category.
4. The large parking lot indicator has an average value of 3.86 including in the appropriate category.
5. The expansion indicator has an average value of 3.78 including in the strategic category.
6. The environment indicator has an average value of 3.93 including in the strategic category.
7. Competition indicators have an average value of 3.95 including in the strategic category.

Based on the recapitulation of consumer assessments, the access indicator shows the highest average value of 4.09. Traffic shows the lowest average value of 3.75. Meanwhile, the average location recapitulation of 3.88 with a strategic interpretation means that the location of Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor is in a strategic location making it easier for consumers to make purchases.

Consumer Responses to Price

Consumer responses regarding the price variable have the following recapitulation:

1. The price affordability indicator has an average value of 3.91, including in the affordable category.
2. The indicator of price compatibility with product quality has an average value of 3.90 including in the appropriate category.
3. The price competitiveness indicator has an average value of 3.73 including in the competitive category.
4. The indicator of price compatibility with benefits has an average value of 3.84 including in the appropriate category.

Based on the recapitulation of consumer assessments, it states that the price affordability indicator shows the highest average value of 3.91. Price competitiveness shows the lowest average value of 3.73. While the average recapitulation of prices is 3.85 with interpretation is appropriate, meaning that the price offered by Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor is in accordance with what consumers get.

Consumer Responses to Product Design

Consumer responses regarding product design variables have the following recapitulation:

1. The shape indicator has an average value of 4.03, including in the good category.

2. The feature indicator has an average value of 3.82 including in the good category.
3. The style indicator has an average value of 3.87 including in the good category.

Based on the recapitulation of consumer assessments, it states that the shape indicator shows the highest average value of 4.03. Features show the lowest average value of 3.82. Meanwhile, the average recapitulation of product design is 3.91 with a good interpretation, meaning that the product design offered by Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor gives a good impression for consumers to make purchases.

Consumer Responses to Purchase Interest

Consumer responses regarding the purchase interest variable have the following recapitulation:

1. The transactional interest indicator has an average value of 3.84, including in the high category.
2. The referential interest indicator has an average value of 3.76 including in the high category.
3. Preferential interest indicators have an average value of 3.78 including in the high category.
4. The exploratory interest indicator has an average value of 3.77 including in the high category.

Based on the recapitulation of consumer assessments, it states that the transactional interest indicator shows the highest average value of 3.84. Referential interest shows the lowest average value of 3.76. Meanwhile, the recapitulation of buying interest is 3.79 with a high interpretation, meaning that consumers already believe in buying products at Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression was carried out to determine the effect of location, price and product design on consumer buying interest in Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.

Table 2. Multiple Linear Regression Coefficientsa

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	0,099	3,197		,031	,975
	Location	,104	,044	,162	2,377	,019
	Price	,320	,092	,308	3,462	,001
	Product Design	,629	,116	,479	5,410	,000

Depe

Indent Variable: Purchase Intention (Y)

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 2, a regression equation with the estimated model is obtained as follows:

$$Y = 0.099 + 0.104X1 + 0.320X2 + 0.629X3 + \epsilon$$

From the regression equation, it is known that the location variable (X1), price (X2) and product design (X3) are positive. So that if the value of the

independent variable, it will be followed by an increase in consumer buying interest in Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

Table 3. Results of Correlation Coefficient and Coefficient of Determination Analysis

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,749 ^a	,561	,547	3,56133

a. Predictors: (Constant), Product Design, Location, Price

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

Source: Data Processed,2022

From Table 3, it can be seen that the R value is 0.749, which shows the correlation value or relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, namely buying interest (Y) has a strong correlation (0.601-0.800), meaning that when the independent variable increases, it will be followed by an increase in the dependent variable Sugiyono (2019: 267). This shows that the increasing location (X₁), price (X₂) and product design (X₃) will have a positive effect on consumer buying interest in Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.

Coefficient of Determination Analysis

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the amount of R square is 0.561 or 56.1%. This shows that the percentage contribution of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable is 56.1%, while the remaining 43.9% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study such as factors of encouragement from within the individual, social motive factors and emotional factors (Fajar, 2016: 194).

F-test

The F-test is used to see the effect of the independent variables, namely location (X₁), price (X₂) and product design (X₃) simultaneously on the dependent variable (dependent) purchase intention (Y).

Table 4. Simultaneous Regression Testing

Model	Sum Of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	1557,018	3	519,006	40,921	<,001 ^b
Residual					
Total					
Residual	1217,572	96	12,683		
Total	2774,590	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Product Design, Location, Price

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 4 that the value that the F_{count} value is 40.921 which will be compared with F_{table}, to find out F_{table}, it is necessary to calculate using a significance level of 0.05 (α = 5%) with degrees of freedom (df = n-k) or 100 - 3 - 1 = 96. By looking at the results of freedom, the F_{table} value of 2.699 is obtained,

which shows that F_{count} is greater than F_{table} ($40.921 > 2.699$), therefore it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, meaning that the independent variables location (X_1), price (X_2) and product design (X_3) simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on buying interest in Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.

Test t

The t test is conducted to compare t_{count} with t_{table} . If t_{count} is greater than t_{table} ($t_{count} > t_{table}$), it indicates that the independent variable partially affects the dependent variable.

Table 5. Partial Regression Testing Model Summary^b

Coefficients ^a		
Model	T	Sig.
1 (Constant)	,031	,975
Location	2,377	,019
Price	3,462	,001
Product Design	5,410	,000

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 5 above, the t_{count} value and the significance value of each independent variable can be seen. While the t_{table} value for $\alpha = 0.05$ with a degree of freedom of $100 - 3 - 1 = 96$ is 1.661, thus the partial test results are obtained as follows:

Table 6. Recapitulation of Partial Testing

No	Variables	Tcount	Ttabel	Sig.	A	Purchase Intention	Kesimpulan
1	Location	2,377	1,661	,019	0,05	Ha1 accepted	Location has a positive and significant effect on buying interest.
2	Price	3,462	1,661	,001	0,05	Ha2 accepted	Price has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.
3	Product Design	5,410	1,661	,000	0,05	Ha3 accepted	Product design has a positive and significant effect on buying interest.

Source: Data Processed, 2022

Based on Table 6, it can be seen that the independent variables, namely location (X_1), price (X_2) and product design (X_3) have a partially positive and significant effect on the dependent variable, namely purchase intention (Y). This is indicated by the t_{count} value of all these variables greater than the t_{table} . The product design variable (X_3) is the most dominant variable in its influence on buying interest (Y).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research and hypothesis testing that has been carried out, conclusions can be drawn:

1. Based on consumer research Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor on location, price, product design and purchase intention, it can be concluded that consumer responses are as follows:

- a. Consumer assessment of location has an average value of 3.88
 - b. Consumer assessment of price has an average value of 3.85
 - c. Consumer assessment regarding product design have an average value of 3.91
 - d. Consumer assessment of buying interest has an average value of 3.79
2. The results of location research, price and product design simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on buying interest.
 3. The results of the study partially location, price and product design have a positive and significant effect on buying interest.

Based on the results of the study, the suggestions that the authors can propose are as follows:

1. For location, the company should pay attention to the ease with which consumers can reach Sri Jaya Meubel Bogor.
2. For prices, the company should determine the selling price must adjust to competitors' prices in order to help the company generate more sales.
3. For product design, companies should be advised to improve features that keep up with the times so that consumers are interested in the products offered.
4. For buying interest, the company should be able to make consumers satisfied with what the product provides so that good consumer reviews will influence other people in making choices.
5. For further researchers, this research can be used as a reference and reference. Further researchers are advised to look for other variables that influence buying interest such as.

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